

Making Complex Programs Legible to Decision-Makers

The RECAP© Framework for Constructing Program Theory Using Results-Based Management

Description: Most teams can eventually describe what they want (results) and the types of activities they have to design to get there. Where projects succeed or fail is the space in between activities and results: the risks, evidence, context, assumptions, and people factors that shape whether activities actually lead to results. RECAP is a structured way to examine that space —so programs becomes legible to decision-makers and support measurable change.

Citation: Salehi, Roxana, Making Complex Programs Legible to Decision-Makers
The RECAP© Framework for Constructing Program Theory Using Results-Based Management, V.2, 2026,
www.vitusHQ.com

R RISK

What could go wrong, and can we plan for it?

As you write the narrative for each outcome pathway, consult your risk registry. If you don't have a risk registry, make one.

What knowledge, data, or experience informs our approach?

As you write each outcome pathway, see if you can incorporate evidence from any of these sources:

- Scientific research
- Previous evaluations
- Stakeholder /expert knowledge
- Gender & human rights analysis
- Environmental analysis
- Costing studies
- Environmental scans/scoping review

E EVIDENCE

What political, social, regulatory institutional, and individual-level factors shape this intervention?

Consider these levels :

1. Individual-Level:
 - e.g., baseline capabilities, demographics
2. Organizational-Level
 - e.g., leadership, culture, internal capacity
3. Environmental/Sociopolitical
 - e.g., policies, climate, natural disasters, wars
4. Regulatory (e.g. AI Act, EHDS)

C CONTEXT

As you write each outcome pathway, ask: **What needs to be true for this pathway to work as planned?**

A ASSUMPTIONS

P PEOPLE

As you write each outcome pathway, ask: **Who are the key players, what roles do they play, and how will they be affected by the intervention along this pathway?**

Making Complex Programs Legible to Decision-Makers

The RECAP© Framework for Constructing Program Theory

Using Results-Based Management

Citation: Salehi, Roxana, Constructing Program Theory Using a Practical Tool based on Results-Based Management: The RECAP© Framework, V.2, 2026, www.vitusHQ.com

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